

Investigation of Interleaved Boost Converter with Voltage multiplier for PV with Fuzzy MPPT

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ABSTRACT

This paper depicts the significance of Interleaved Boost Converter (IBC) with diode-capacitor multiplier with PV as the input source. Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) was used to obtain maximum power from the PV system. In this, interleaving topology is used to reduce the input current ripple, output voltage ripple, power loss and to suppress the ripple in battery current in the case of Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicle (PHEV). Moreover, voltage multiplier cells are added in the IBC configuration to reduce the narrow turn-off periods. Two MPPT techniques are compared in this paper: i) Perturb and Observe (P&O) algorithm ii) Fuzzy Logic. The two algorithms are simulated using MATLAB and the comparison of performance parameters like the ripple is done and the results are verified.

KEY WORDS:

IBC, Photovoltaic panels, MPPT, PHEV

1.INTRODUCTION

Recently, there is an increase in energy consumption in India due to enormous population growth and economic development in India. So, there is a need to search for alternative energy resources other than the conventional energy sources to suffice the population with the power demand and also as the non-renewable energy resources are getting depleted which leaves us with the option of acquiring power from resource that is available to us almost endlessly. The renewable energy resources are a great option and their usage is also greatly increasing these days.

India being a sunshine country, the use of photovoltaic solar cells (PVSCs) provides energy conservation, helps in demand-side management and would be an optimal solution to our problems since the solar energy is free and pollution free. In order to obtain maximum power from the PV system, MPPT techniques are used. It is used to maximise the PV array output power by tracking continuously the maximum power point.

In this paper, P&O and Fuzzy MPPT have been simulated and compared. The P&O is dominantly used in practical PV systems for the MPPT control due to its simple reliability and its tracking efficiency. Perturbation method either increases or decreases the voltage reference of the PWM signal which will in turn vary the PV output power. This method is simple but the operating voltage in PV panel is always varying in nature and it has to be monitored and tracked continuously for the next perturbation cycle. To solve this, a fuzzy logic based MPPT is discussed in this paper so that the maximum power point can be tracked faster and the fluctuation in PV voltage can also be minimised. The MPPT is simulated using MATLAB/SIMULINK and used along with the IBC with the diode-capacitor multiplier.

II. PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEM

A.Introduction

PV systems can generate electricity with low maintenance cost and simple operation. But the initial cost is high which prevents the consumers to go for solar PV in larger scale. However, these are employed for numerous applications as reported in literature [1].

The block diagram of the IBC with PV system is shown in Figure.1.

Figure1: Block diagram of IBC with PV system

The PV cell is as shown below in Figure.2

Figure: 2 PV cell modeled as diode circuit

B.Design Equations

The PV system can be modeled by designing the parameters using the following formulas.[2]

The module photo-current is given by:

$$(1) I_{ph} = [I_{SCr} + K_i(T - 298)] * \lambda / 1000$$

The value of the module reverse saturation current I_{rs} is given by:

$$(2) I_{rs} = I_{SCr} / [\exp(\frac{qV_{oc}}{N_s AkT}) - 1]$$

The module saturation current varies with the cell temperature which is given by:

$$(3) I_0 = I_{rs} \left(\frac{T}{T_r} \right)^3 \exp \left(q * \frac{E_{g0}}{B_k} \left\{ \frac{1}{T_r} - \frac{1}{T} \right\} \right)$$

The current output of PV module is given by the equation (4) by considering $V_{pv} = V_{oc}$, $N_p = 1$ and $N_s = 36$

$$(4) \quad I_{PV} = N_p * I_{ph} - N_p * I_0 \left[\exp \left\{ \frac{q(V_{PV} + I_{PV}R_S)}{N_s AkT} \right\} - 1 \right]$$

where V_{pv} is output voltage of a PV module (V)

I_{pv} is output current of a PV module (A)

T_r is the reference temperature = 298 K

T is the module operating temperature in Kelvin

I_{ph} is the light generated current in a PV module (A)

I_0 is the PV module saturation current (A)

A = B is an ideality factor = 1.6

k is Boltzman constant = 1.3805×10^{-23} J/K

q is Electron charge = 1.6×10^{-19} C

R_s is the series resistance of a PV module

I_{SCr} is the PV module short-circuit current at 25°C and $1000\text{W/m}^2 = 2.55\text{A}$

K_i is the short-circuit current temperature co-efficient at

$I_{SCr} = 0.0017\text{A} / ^\circ\text{C}$

λ is the PV module illumination (W/m^2) = 1000W/m^2

E_{go} is the band gap for silicon = 1.1 eV

N_s is the number of cells connected in series

N_p is the number of cells connected in parallel

C.Simulation of PV

PV was simulated in MATLAB under the following conditions: *i) With varying irradiation and fixed temperature:* The range of irradiation is around 200 W/m^2 to 1000 W/m^2 keeping the temperature at 25°C . *ii) With varying temperature and constant insolation :* The temperature range is about 25°C to 75°C keeping irradiation at 1 W/m^2 .

Figure.3 shows the simulation model of PV.

Figure:3 Simulation of PV

The plots between power vs. voltage and current vs. voltage were plotted for the above mentioned two cases. The figures 4.a and 4.b shows the P-V and I-V curves for varying irradiation data and constant temperature respectively. Figures 5.a and 5.b shows the P-V and I-V curves for varying temperature and constant irradiation data respectively.

Figure:4.a P-V curve for case i) Figure:4.b I-V curve for case ii)

Figure:5.a P-V curve for case ii) Figure:5.b. I-V curve for case ii)

I. MAXIMUM POWER POINT TRACKING

A. PERTURB AND OBSERVE ALGORITHM

Perturb and Observe algorithm is also known as “Hill Climbing”. It is a simple feedback structure which uses fewer measured parameters. The P&O algorithm works on the basis of perturbing the terminal voltage of the array based on the output power of the photovoltaic system with that of the previous cycle. If there is an increase in the array power resulting from the perturbation, then the following perturbation is done or continued in the same direction. If there is a decrease then, there the perturbation is to be done in the opposite direction in order to increase the power. In this way, the peak power is tracked continuously until the Maximum Power Point (MPP) is reached. If the atmospheric condition is such that it varies continuously, then the tracking takes a longer time to settle down[3]. Figure 6 shows the flowchart of the P&O algorithm.

Figure:6 Flowchart of P&O algorithm

A.Fuzzy Logic Control Based MPPT

The inputs to the FLC MPPT are the measured PV panel output voltage and current. PV power and the variation in power with respect to the voltage is to be evaluated. Based on the dp/dv and $\Delta dp/dv$ values, the voltage reference of the PWM signal is determined[5]. FLC uses fuzzy set theory in which the variables are members of one or more sets. The FLC tries to match the reasoning of humans and to compute the imprecise information, make decisions based on unclear data and by applying the final defuzzification process, it arrives at the exact conclusion[6].

It uses three steps for the control:

- i) Fuzzification
- ii) Inference
- iii) Defuzzification

i) Fuzzification:

The input and output variables are expressed in fuzzy sets here using linguistic levels. The levels are adjacent intervals which form the membership function. The value of a member denote the extent to which it can belong. This process of converting the variables into linguistic levels is known as Fuzzification.

ii) Inference:

The control surface is found out using the set of rules which gives the relation between the input and output variables. The conventional rule would be

If x is A THEN y is B

If the input variables and the set of rules are read properly and if it is true, then it leads to the surface formation. In a similar way, each rule is satisfied and the control surface that is formed is formulated as a fuzzy set. This is referred as Inference.

iii) Defuzzification:

The fuzzy variable is converted into a crisp variable which is known as defuzzification. There are various methods but the centroid method is the most popularly used. In this method, the error (E) and changing error (CE) are defined as input variables:

$$E(k) = \frac{dP}{dV} = \frac{P(k) - P(k-1)}{V(k) - V(k-1)} \quad (5)$$

$$CE(k) = E(k) - E(k-1) \quad (6)$$

The rules that were used for the MPPT control is shown in the table.1 below:

Table .1 Rules for Fuzzy MPPT

E \ CE	NB	NS	ZE	PS	PB
NB	ZE	ZE	NB	NB	NB
NS	NS	ZE	NS	NS	NS
ZE	NM	ZE	ZE	ZE	PM
PS	PM	PS	PS	ZE	ZE
PB	PB	PB	ZE	ZE	ZE

The Error(E) and Change in error (CE) and the output variable is represented below in the figures 7,8 &9 respectively.

Figure:7 Membership function of Error (E)

Figure:8 Membership function of Change in Error (CE)

Figure:9 Membership function of the output variable

Simulation Results

The simulation of the P&O and Fuzzy MPPT algorithms were done in the MATLAB. Figure 10 shows the MATLAB/SIMULINK circuit of the P&O.

Figure:10 Simulation circuit of P&O algorithm

The voltage and current are derived from the PV panel and the dP/dV is derived and from its value, the output of the P&O is derived. This gives the duty ratio and thus the pulse for the switches. Figures 11 & 12 show the MPPT output of P&O and the pulse generated from it.

Figure: 11 MPPT output of P&O

Figure:12 Pulse generated using P&O

The pulse were generated for a duty ratio of 0.5 and they are phase shifted by 180° in the acse of IBC topology because of interleaving principle. The simulation circuit is shown in figure 13.

Figure: 13 Simulation circuit of Fuzzy Logic Control based MPPT

Here, the error dP/dV and the change in error $\Delta dP/dV$ is calculated and based on it the duty ratio and thus pulses to the switches is controlled. Figures 14 & 15 show the FLC output and the pulse generated using it.

Figure:14 FLC based MPPT output

Figure 15 shows the comparison between the MPPT output and the reference signal that was generated.

Figure: 15 Generation of pulse using FLC

The pulses were genrated with 0.5 duty ratio and it was shifted by about 180° for the other switch of the IBC.

III. IBC WITH DIODE-CAPACITOR MULTIPLIER

A.Introduction

Generally, voltage multiplier cells are added in the conventional IBC circuit to circumvent narrow turn-off period and to reduce the current ripple. Interleaved structure is used at the input side to distribute the input current and the voltage multiplier is incorporated in the output side to achieve a high step-up gain. The stress that is applied on the switches is considerably reduced as the ripple reduces [7].

The diode-capacitor multiplier cells helps to boost up the conversion ratio at low duty cycle with reduced voltage stress across the devices. For the proposed topology, only one stage of voltage multiplier cell is employed to reduce the circuit complexity [8].

The Interleaved structure increases the power factor and the THD is improved by about 40% when compared to the conventional boost converter when used for the battery charging application of a PHEV. The Interleaved structure also reduces the battery charging current and it is used for limited power levels.

The circuit diagram of the IBC with diode-capacitor multiplier is shown in the figure 16.

Figure:16 Circuit of the IBC with diode-capacitor multiplier

B.Design Equations

The equations that are required to design the elements of diode-capacitor multiplier are as follows.

The conversion ratio here is given by[9]:

$$M = \frac{u_0}{u_{in}} = \frac{n+1}{1-D} \quad (7)$$

where u_0 and u_{in} are the input and output voltages and n is the number of the multiplier cells.

The inductors and capacitors are designed using the formulas:

$$L = \frac{V_{in} D}{\Delta I_L f_s} \quad (8)$$

where V_{in} is the input voltage, f_s is the switching frequency and ΔI_L is the ripple content in the Inductor current.

$$C = \frac{D V_0 T}{R \Delta V_0} \quad (9)$$

where V_0 is the output voltage is the time period is the resistance, ΔV_0 is the ripple of the output voltage and D is the duty ratio.

C.Simulation results

The simulation of the IBC with the diode-capacitor multiplier was done with the P&O MPPT and the FLC based MPPT. The simulation parameters that were used are listed below in the table.2.

Table:2 Simulation parameters for the IBC with diode-capacitor multiplier

Duty Ratio δ	0.5
Input voltage V_{in}	40V
Frequency f_s	50kHz
Capacitor C1	100 μ F
Capacitor C0	40 μ F
Inductors L1,L2	640 μ H

The figure 17 shows the simulation result of the P&O with the IBC circuit.

Figure: 17 Output voltage of the P&O with the IBC circuit

The output voltage obtained is about 164.5 V .Figure18 shows the simulation result of the IBC with the FLC MPPT.

Figure: 18 Output voltage of the IBC with the FLC MPPT

An output voltage of about 167V was obtained with FLC MPPT. The comparison in terms of the output voltage and output voltage ripple is done for both the MPPT and it is shown in the table 3.

Table 3 Ripple comparison between the P&O and the FLC MPPT

	Output voltage (V)	Output voltage ripple(%)
P&O	164.5	0.910
Fuzzy	167	0.175

The comparison shows that the ripple is less in the FLC MPPT than in the P&O. So, the FLC MPPT is chosen as the best one and used along with the IBC with diode-capacitor multiplier for PHEV.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the P&O and Fuzzy MPPT with IBC and diode-capacitor multiplier. The IBC when implemented with the diode-capacitor multiplier gives minimum output voltage ripple, input current ripple and power losses across the switches. While comparing the P&O and Fuzzy MPPT, the FLC based MPPT gives lesser output voltage ripple and higher output voltage when used to give pulses to the switches for the IBC. Thus IBC with voltage multiplier is a better configuration for PV.

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